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“Genetic Variability at An Allosteric site of SARS-CoV-2 RNA-dependent RNA polymerase Across Coronaviruses and SARS-CoV-2 Samples”

SARS-CoV-2 is a positive-strand RNA virus, depending on its multi-subunit machinery to replicate its RNA. This machinery is known as RNA-dependent RNA polymerase (RdRp). The catalytic subunit of RdRp, which is the core component of this machinery, is called nsp12. Nsp12 has little catalytic activity on its own and relies on accessory subunits to have full activity. These accessory factors, nsp7 and nsp8, increase RdRp template binding and processivity. (Yin et al., 2020)

RdRp is a well-established target for a class of antiviral drugs known as nucleotide analogs. Remdesivir is an example of such a group of drugs that inhibits RdRp. Remdesivir has been authorized to be used for special COVID-19 cases with severe symptoms in Canada. (<https://healthykanadians.gc.ca/recall-alert-rappel-avis/hc-sc/2020/73621a-eng.php>)

We previously analyzed the remdesivir-binding site of RdRp. We then shifted our focus on another druggable pocket of the RdRp complex, an allosteric site on the RdRp complex, which is this post's topic.

In figure 1, we show the RdRp complex and highlight the site of interest, which is lined by amino acid residue M666 and which we refer to here as the M666 pocket. This site has a druggability score of 1.008 based on our results from Sitemap (Schrodinger, NY), indicating a druggable site (figure 2).

M666 site is at the nsp8 binding site of nsp12. A compound binding this site with high potency may antagonize the formation of an active RdRp complex. It may inhibit the RdRp function, which is necessary for viral replication.

Figure 1. The apo nsp12-nsp7-nsp8 RdRp complex and the positioning of the M666 pocket at the interface of nsp12-nsp8.

Figure 2. Druggability assessment of the M666 pocket.

We then selected the residues surrounding the part of the pocket, which is in proximity to bound nsp8. The RdRp M666 pocket is lined by 24 amino acid sidechains: L271, Y273, P323, T324, S325, F326, G327, P328, L329, V330, R331, T344, G345, Y346, R349, H355, P378, A379, A382, F396, V398, S664, M666, V675.

Figure 3. The 24 amino acid sidechains surrounding M666 pocket at nsp12-nsp8 interface.

We conduct a broad survey of viral proteins from Alpha- and Betacoronaviruses to identify the most conserved druggable sites. We are integrating variability and druggability data to infer the most promising strategies for developing broad-spectrum viral inhibitors. This analysis can be valuable in the context of the emergence of future coronaviruses circulating in bat reservoir species.

To assess this site's genetic variability, we first looked at 27 reviewed sequences from Uniprot, of which 6 are from the Alphacoronavirus genus and 21 from the Betacoronavirus genus. In figure 4, the diversity dendrogram shows the two clusters of Alphacoronavirus and Betacoronavirus organisms. The letters of varying sizes show the profile of residues at each specific amino acid position. For example, at position L271 (SARS-CoV-2 residue), we see that entries have either a leucine, a cysteine, a threonine, or a valine. Altogether, eight out of twenty-four residues at M666 were identical across the 27 entries, equivalent to 33% identity at this site. Compared with the active site (where Remdesivir binds), which has 83% identity, this pocket is poorly conserved.

Figure 4. The diversity dendrogram of M666 site for the entries of Alpha- and Betacoronavirus genera.

If we only look across the 21 Betacoronavirus sequences (the genus of SARS-CoV-2 virus), we see a 50% conservation of residues at the M666 site, which includes these twelve out of the twenty-four residues: Y273, T324, F326, G327, P328, V330, G345, Y346, P378, A379, V398, V675.

Figure 5. The diversity dendrogram of M666 site for the entries of Betacoronavirus genus.

As a follow-up to assessing the genetic variability among Alphacoronavirus and Betacoronavirus entries, our collaborator, Nicola De Maio, from Nick Goldman’s lab at the European Bioinformatics Institute has identified the non-synonymous mutations at M666 sites across

more than 15000 SARS-CoV-2 samples. Altogether he identified non-synonymous mutations at 10 unique amino acid residues consisting of 13 unique non-synonymous variants. In table 1, there are details about the mutation events underlying these variants. This indicates significant genetic variability compared with the Remdesivir site, where only 8 out of 48 residues were mutated.

index	Wild type amino acid in SARS-CoV-2	Non-synonymous variants	Codon one	Codon two	Codon three	Source of the Variants
1	P323	P (5012)	c (15870) t (5)	c (5013) t (10839)	t (15875)	4 different mutation events are inferred for the 5 observed t variants , observed in samples from 5 different locations
		1 S (1)				
		2 L (10835)				
		3 F (4)				
2	T324	T (15871)	a (15875)	c (15871) t (1)	a (15874)	
		4 I (1)				
3	P328	P (15872)	c (15872) t (2)	c (15874)	a (15874)	single mutation event and variants observed in China and England
		5 S (2)				
4	L329	L (15869)	a (5) c (15869)	t (15874)	a (15874)	5 I variants from a single mutation event, all variants from India
		6 I (5)				
5	R349	R (15865)	a (15866) g (1)	g (15867)	a (15865) c (1) g (1)	
		7 S (1)				
		8 G (1)				
6	H355	H (15866)	c (15866) t (1)	a (15867)	t (15867)	
		9 Y (1)				
7	A379	A (15843)	g (15844)	c (15843) t (1)	t (15844)	
		10 V (1)				
8	A382	A (15846)	g (15856)	c (15847) t (9)	t (15855)	9 V variants seemingly from 4 different mutation events, samples with the variant from Taiwan, England, Denmark, and China
		11 V (9)				
9	M666	M (15845)	a (15872)	t (15875)	g (15848) t (27)	I variant seen in samples from Spain, Scotland, Wales, NI, USA-NY, Netherlands, apparently from a single mutation event
		12 I (27)				
10	V675	V (15873)	g (15874) t (1)	t (15875)	t (15874)	
		13 F (1)				

Table 1. The non-synonymous variants at RdRp M666 site across more than 15000 SARS-CoV-2 samples. (Nicola De Maio, 2020). The source of the variants is highlighted in bold font.

Most remarkable is P323, which is very variable in the current outbreak and was also highly variable across coronavirus strains (Figures 4). In the absence of any ligand for the M666 site, we cannot predict how these mutations might affect ligand-binding.

In comparison to [the remdesivir binding site of RdRp, which is very well-conserved \(83%\)](#) among the entries of alphacoronavirus and betacoronavirus entries, the M666 site is poorly conserved (33%). In terms of druggability score (Dscore), M666 pocket (Dscore=1.028) is superior to remdesivir site (Dscore=0.859). While remdesivir is among a well-known and well-established group of antivirals known as nucleotide analogs, its use for COVID-19 is only recommended for hospitalized patients due to COVID-19 and need supplemental oxygen therapy. (Clinical Trials.gov number, NCT04280705) Only in those cases, remdesivir was superior to placebo in shortening the time to recovery. (Goldman et al., 2020) This phase3 study showed that despite remdesivir, there was still high mortality because of COVID-19. Therefore, clinically we still need a better drug to treat COVID19 through different approaches. (<https://www.nejm.org/doi/full/10.1056/NEJMoa2007764>)

Targeting the M666 provides an alternate strategy to target RdRp function by disturbing its interaction with a key accessory factor, nsp8. It is important to note the high genetic variability of this site among coronaviruses and SARS-CoV-2 samples, which deprioritizes it as a target for pan-coronavirus anti-SARS-CoV-2 drugs.

References:

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